

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

3rd TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Experimental validation of optimized Copper-based Catalysts and FLOW reactors for the electrochemical conversion of CO₂ to valuable chemicals and REnewable fuels
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	C²FLOW-CO₂RE
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	Fundació Institut de Recerca en Energia de Catalunya (IREC), Advanced Materials for Energy (M4E) Laboratory
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Electrocatalysis, Reactor design, Electrochemical CO ₂ utilisation, Material characterization, Prototype testing
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	2nd April 2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	14th May 2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	3rd April 2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	13th May 2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	13
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	12 of the days exclusively correspond to Saturdays and Sundays during the access period (the RI was fully accessible during the weekdays). In addition, 1st of May is a national holiday in Spain.
Number of days using the RI	28
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	The PhD student involved in the research, was able to fully access the facilities required for the project at IREC's M4E. The PhD student was also well supported by IREC's M4E.

Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results

Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)

The overall aim of the project was to validate the innovative Cu-based electrocatalysts and continuous flow reactor (CFR) designs developed at UoE for the efficient and scalable electrochemical conversion of CO₂ into valuable chemicals and renewable fuels, leveraging state-of-the-art research facilities at the M4E Laboratory in IREC. The objectives of this research were:

- Evaluation of UoE's novel Cu and CuAg catalysts for the electrochemical conversion of CO₂ to ethylene and ethanol under commercially relevant conditions (i.e. current densities of 200 mA/cm²).
- Validation of UoE's innovative gas and electrolyte flow compartment designs with optimised flow distribution under commercially relevant conditions (i.e. current densities of 200 mA/cm²).

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The research at the core of the **C²FLOW-CO₂RE** project consisted of two work packages:

WP1: Experimental evaluation of Cu and CuAg catalysts

During WP1, Cu and CuAg electrocatalysts already developed at The University of Edinburgh (UoE) were evaluated at M4E's research facilities. The Cu and CuAg electrocatalysts had been previously electrodeposited on commercial GDLs at UoE under different current densities (8, 15 and 30 mA/cm²) from a sulfate electrolyte, enabling the fabrication of GDEs with Cu and CuAg catalysts with different crystal structure, composition and catalyst size/distribution. The whole material characterisation (FIB-SEM with EDX, XRD and ECSA) of the resulting GDEs was completed at UoE to ensure that the activities conducted at IREC would focus on the evaluation of the electrochemical performance of the GDEs equipped with Cu and CuAg electrocatalysts.

The evaluation of the electrochemical performance of the GDEs equipped with Cu and CuAg electrocatalysts was conducted at IREC's M4E research facilities. The GDEs with the Cu and CuAg electrocatalysts were assembled within M4E's current CFR platform equipped with a commercial filter-press electrochemical flow cell (Micro Flow Cell from Electrocell A/S). The gas stream leaving the CFR was directly connected to a gas chromatography (GC) system (Shimadzu GC-2030) equipped with a Carboxen[®]-1010 PLOT column and a barrier discharge ionization detector (BID) to detect and quantify all the gas products generated during the experiments. Liquid products, on the other hand, were detected and quantified using both a head space (HS)-GC and ion chromatography (IC) systems, depending on their nature: whereas alcohols were analysed by HS-GC with a Shimadzu GC-2010 system equipped with a HP-PLOT column, acetate and formate were analysed with a Dionex ICS-1100 IC equipment equipped with a Dionex Ion Pac AS-22 anion exchange column and a chemical suppressor (ASR-ultra 4mm).

Following a recent collaboration between IREC and UoE currently under review for publication (submitted to Advanced Energy Materials), it was decided to conduct the electrochemical evaluation in aqueous 1 M KOH at different current densities (50, 100, 150 and 200 mA/cm²) to evaluate the efficiency and selectivity of the Cu and CuAg catalysts.

WP2: Experimental validation of optimized flow reactors

CFRs with different design iterations of electrolyte and gas flow compartments already developed at UoE using advanced CAD tools (i.e. Inventor and COMSOL Multiphysics) and manufactured by 3D printing were also evaluated at IREC's M4E research facilities using the best GDEs from WP1. M4E's current CFR platform was adapted for this, where their commercial filter-press electrochemical flow cell was replaced by UoE's newly designed filter-press electrochemical reactor. The same techniques previously mentioned for the analysis and quantification of products (e.g. GC, HS-GC, IC), as well as the same operating conditions (e.g. electrolyte, current density) were used during WP1.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Ongoing efforts are being dedicated to the evaluation and curation of all of the experimental data obtained. However, an initial set of results can be presented below, which already pinpoint to the success of the project.

Fig. 1 displays the Faradaic efficiency (FE) of Cu electrocatalysts electrodeposited at three different current densities over commercial GDLs at UoE, 8 mA/cm² (Fig. 1A), 15 mA/cm² (Fig. 1B) and 30 mA/cm² (Fig. 1C), for the different products analysed: hydrogen, carbon monoxide, methane, ethylene, formic acid, methanol, ethanol and propanol. In all cases, the sum of FE values was between 80 and 100%, confirming the suitability of the analytical work conducted in identifying the main products of the process. In all cases, FE for the main target product, ethylene, increased as the current density was raised, with a maximum of 35.3% with the Cu electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 15 mA cm⁻² when the applied current density was 200 mA cm⁻². In those same conditions with the same electrode, FE values of 8.4% and 2.7% were achieved, resulting in a combined FE of 46.4% for C₂₊ products from CO₂. Cu electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 30 mA cm⁻² performed slightly worst in relation to ethylene production (FE of 30%), but substantially better for ethanol and ethylene (FE values of 12.6% and 3.6%, respectively), resulting in a total FE of 46.2% for C₂₊ products. Moreover, the parasitic hydrogen evolution reaction in this latter case was significantly inhibited (FE below 25%), demonstrating how just subtle changes in the manufacturing technique of the electrocatalysts (current density in this case) can influence their performance, even in those cases where the electrocatalysts have the same composition and crystal orientation (e.g. these results are not included as were not obtained in IREC; they will be included in the manuscripts under preparation).

Figure 1. Faradaic efficiency values estimated for the main products obtained (left axis) and iR-corrected cathode potentials measured (right axis) in CO₂ electrolysis experiments conducted in a laboratory CFR operating at various current densities with different GDEs: A) commercial GDLs

with Cu electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 8 mA cm^{-2} , B) commercial GDL with Cu electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 15 mA cm^{-2} , and C) commercial GDL with Cu electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 15 mA cm^{-2} .

The data showed above can also be analysed in the form of partial current densities, as show in Fig. 2. By presenting the data this way, one can better differentiate the electrocatalytic properties of each electrode towards the production of each product. One clear result is that, in the case of hydrogen (Fig. 2A), methane (Fig. 2C), ethylene (Fig. 2D), ethanol (Fig. 2G) and propanol (Fig. 2H), the plots of partial current density vs *i*R-corrected electrode potential could be clearly fitted to exponential theoretical curves obtained with the Butler-Volmer equation (theoretical expression describing electrochemical kinetics; more details will be included in manuscripts under preparation). In the case of carbon monoxide (Fig. 2B), we could clearly see that the data did not follow Butler-Volmer; this would be expected, as carbon monoxide is a well-known reaction intermediate in the production of C_{2+} products. In the case of methanol (Fig. 2F), where a clear fit with Butler-Volmer was observed with Cu electrocatalysts produced at 30 mA cm^{-2} , no clear fitting could be obtained with those electrocatalysts electrodeposited at either 8 mA cm^{-2} or 15 mA cm^{-2} due to the very little amount of methanol produced; poorer selectivity towards methanol could be a potential cause for that, which would be further favored by the need to apply more negative potentials to achieve a total current density of 200 mA cm^{-2} with the Cu electrocatalysts produced at 30 mA cm^{-2} . The case of formic acid is particularly interesting: initially, the partial current density increased as the potential moved towards more negative; however, the partial current slightly decrease at the highest applied current density. Although the data obtained with Cu electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 8 and 15 mA cm^{-2} could still fit the Butler-Volmer equation if one takes into account data uncertainty, the results indicate that something else could be taking place involving formic acid.

Figure 2. Partial current densities for different products vs *i*R-corrected cathode potentials measured in CO_2 electrolysis experiments conducted in a laboratory CFR operating at various current densities ($50, 100, 150$ and 200 mA cm^{-2}) using different GDEs (commercial GDLs with Cu electrocatalysts electrodeposited at $8, 15$ and 30 mA cm^{-2}): A) hydrogen, B) carbon monoxide, C) methane, D) ethylene, E) formic acid, F) methanol, G) ethanol, H) propanol.

Fig. 3 displays FE values for all of the products analysed and obtained with CuAg electrocatalysts also electrodeposited at the same three current densities used before over commercial GDLs: 8

mA/cm² (Fig. 3A), 15 mA/cm² (Fig. 3B) and 30 mA/cm² (Fig. 3C). The sum of FE values was between 90 and 100% in all cases, confirming again the validity of the analysis conducted to identify and quantify the main products of the process. The FE for the main target product, ethylene, increased again as the current density was raised; achieving now a maximum of 37.2% with the CuAg electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 8 mA cm⁻² when the applied current density was 200 mA cm⁻². The same electrode operating in those same conditions delivered the highest FE value for ethanol (14.5%), as well as a decent yield for propanol (3.9%), resulting in a combined FE of 55.6% for C₂₊ products from CO₂. Compared to the pure Cu electrocatalysts, all GDEs containing CuAg seemed to inhibit the parasitic hydrogen production reaction quite well, to the point that FE values below 20% were achieved with the CuAg electrocatalysts produced at 15 mA cm⁻².

Figure 3. Faradaic efficiency values estimated for the main products obtained (left axis) and *iR*-corrected cathode potentials measured (right axis) in CO₂ electrolysis experiments conducted in a laboratory CFR operating at various current densities with different GDEs: A) commercial GDLs with CuAg electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 8 mA cm⁻², B) commercial GDL with CuAg electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 15 mA cm⁻², and C) commercial GDL with CuAg electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 15 mA cm⁻².

Partial current density vs *iR*-corrected cathode potential plots for GDEs equipped with CuAg electrocatalysts (Fig. 4) share the same general trends previously observed for the Cu electrocatalysts. Again, the data obtained for hydrogen (Fig. 4A), methane (Fig. 4C), ethylene (Fig. 4D), ethanol (Fig. 4G) and propanol (Fig. 4H) clearly fitted to exponential theoretical curves obtained with the Butler-Volmer equation. The data for carbon monoxide (Fig. 4B) again confirmed carbon monoxide's nature as reaction intermediate, whereas very little methanol (Fig. 2F) was produced with the CuAg electrocatalysts, no matter the current density used in the electrodeposition process (8 mA cm⁻², 15 mA cm⁻² or 30 mA cm⁻²). In the case of formic acid, the data obtained with all the CuAg electrocatalysts did not fit Butler-Volmer at all, and the trend was similar to what was observed for carbon monoxide. This suggests that, contrary to some reports, formic acid may also be a reaction intermediate. Original studies by Bard and co-workers in the late 80s and the ongoing collaboration with IREC (manuscript currently under review in *Advanced Energy Materials*) indicate this, and the data here reported further supports this hypothesis.

Figure 4. Partial current densities for different products vs iR -corrected cathode potentials measured in CO_2 electrolysis experiments conducted in a laboratory CFR operating at various current densities (50, 100, 150 and 200 mA cm^{-2}) using different GDEs (commercial GDLs with CuAg electrocatalysts electrodeposited at 8, 15 and 30 mA cm^{-2}): A) hydrogen, B) carbon monoxide, C) methane, D) ethylene, E) formic acid, F) methanol, G) ethanol, H) propanol.

The data reported above for Cu and CuAg electrocatalysts was obtained with a catalyst loading of 2 C (charged passed during the electrodeposition of Cu and CuAg). Experiments with different loadings (1 C and 3 C) were also conducted during the project, and are currently being analysed. In addition, experiments were conducted with different CFR configurations under the same operating conditions described above. A full set of results will be included in the manuscripts currently under preparation, as well as the PhD student's thesis, which will be submitted later this year.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The results obtained and fully analysed (Figs. 1-4 included in the previous section) demonstrate the importance of the influence of the parameters defined for the synthesis of Cu-based electrocatalysts by electrodeposition methods on the latter performance of such catalysts. Regarding Cu, the resulting current densities were already a result of a preliminary study where, after optimising the process, we realised that higher current densities (8 mA cm^{-2} and higher) were needed to achieve a uniform distribution and structure of electrodeposited Cu electrocatalysts over the surface of commercial GDLs, findings that had not been reported before. This enabled the remarkable combined FE value achieved for C_{2+} products reported above, despite of using just pure Cu catalysts with no alloying metal.

Incorporating Ag into the Cu catalysts further enhance the combined FE observed for C_{2+} products, although the selectivity of the main product of interest, ethylene, did not really improve. Incorporating Ag also seemed to further inhibit the parasitic production of hydrogen, although significantly greater results could be achieved if ionomers were incorporated into the catalysts (e.g. adding the chemicals to the electrodeposition bath would enable that). Still, this study increases the general knowledge related to the electrodeposition of electrocatalysts for the electrodeposition of CO_2 , particularly Cu-based materials.

The preliminary analysis of the data not shown here (e.g. effect of catalyst loading, reactor design) is also quite interesting. Regarding catalyst loading, we can see that its positive (or negative) effect depends on the distribution over the surface. For example, if the distribution is not the greatest (e.g. Cu electrodeposited at 15 mA cm⁻² with a total of 2 C of charge passed), increasing or decreasing the catalyst loading in a 50 % (i.e. 1 C and 3 C of charge passed, respectively) did not result in significant changes in performance. However, when the distribution of electrocatalysts over the surface is perhaps too good (Cu electrodeposited at 30 mA cm⁻² with a total of 2 C of charge passed), it may be necessary to decrease the load (i.e. 1 C of charge passed), as too much catalyst would affect the local mass transport of CO₂ to the surface of the electrocatalyst (i.e. 2 C and especially 3 C). Regarding the design of the CFR, we can see that the initial results also show that, for the same electrode, changes in the flow compartments for both CO₂/gas feed and electrolyte has a remarkable effect on the selectivity and performance, highlighting the need to conduct more research in this area.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The work conducted at IREC has successfully confirmed the suitability of the Cu-based electrocatalysts for CO₂ electrochemical reduction to renewable fuels and valuable chemical commodities developed at UoE. It also helped to understand how the different parameters influencing the fabrication process also affected the performance of the electrocatalysts, and how electrocatalyst loading may affect the performance depending on such parameters.

The best electrocatalysts produced were capable of delivering up to 37.2 % FE for ethylene, 14.5% FE for ethanol and 3.9% for propanol, making a combined FE of 55.6% for C₂₊ products. This results, which were achieved under realistic conditions mimicking those required in industry (current density of 200 mA cm⁻², electrode areas of at least 5 cm²) are encouraging about how the electrochemical conversion of CO₂ to C₂₊ products can be enhanced by optimising the manufacturing process of the electrocatalysts.

Last but not least, preliminary results conducted on CFRs designed, simulated and optimised by advanced CAD tools indicate the importance of optimising the flow of both gas and electrolyte in CFR reactors used for the electrochemical conversion of CO₂.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

We were able to access all of the equipment we had planned to use. There were some very minor technical issues with one of the analytical systems, but the team at M4E were very keen to conduct additional analysis of samples in the weeks following the research visit to overcome this. Moreover, the PhD student involved in the work, faced some challenges with some of the reactor pieces previously manufactured at UoE due to some minor leaks. The technical staff at IREC's M4E did everything possible to minimise this, including the additional 3D printing of reactor pieces following the design/indication.

Overall, we could not be more pleased with the technical support and friendly and professional attitude from every IREC member involved.

Intended publications

During the research visit, we collaborated with IREC on developing a kinetic model to fit our experimental results (Figs. 2 and 4). This model has already been applied to some of IREC's own research, and the following publication has already been produced and submitted:

- Venkata S.R.K. Tandava, Mayra S. Tovar-Oliva, Martí Biset-Peiró, Diouldé Sylla, Joan Ramón Morante, Ignacio Tudela, Sebastián Murcia-López, Modulating the surface interface of PTFE/Cu-based GDEs to boost the electrochemical conversion of CO₂ to C₂H₄ at ultra-low overpotential, submitted to Advanced Energy Materials (under review).

Regarding the project results, it is expected that the following publications will be prepared based on the research conducted:

- - Mayra S. Tovar-Oliva, Venkata S.R.K. Tandava, Caroline Kirk, Sebastián Murcia-López, Ignacio Tudela, Effect of synthesis parameters on the characteristics and performance of electrodeposited Cu catalysts for the electrochemical reduction of CO₂ to chemical commodities, to be submitted to Applied Catalysis B: Environmental (under preparation).
- - Mayra S. Tovar-Oliva, Venkata S.R.K. Tandava, Caroline Kirk, Sebastián Murcia-López, Ignacio Tudela, Electrodeposition of CuAg catalysts for the electrochemical reduction of CO₂, to be submitted to Chemical Engineering Journal (under preparation).
- - Mayra S. Tovar-Oliva, Venkata S.R.K. Tandava, Sebastián Murcia-López, Ignacio Tudela, Design, simulation and optimisation of electrochemical flow reactors for the electrochemical reduction of CO₂, to be submitted to Chemical Engineering Journal (under preparation).

Data management

Data will be available publicly once the publications are available. In this regard, all the publications will be publicly available either in Gold or Green Open Access (internal UoE funding provided by UKRI will be used for Gold Open Access). Additional data will be provided upon request once the publications are published.

Conclusions / additional comments

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The information available on the website was accessible and easy to understand, and the whole process was straightforward.					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Most of the information was clear on how to proceed, although more clarification on deadlines for the research to be conducted/report to be completed would have been welcomed. Nevertheless, this is a very minor thing.					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
The support received from IREC in general and M4E in particular has been OUTSTANDING. The team was friendly professional and extremely helpful throughout the whole project.					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
The RI is top class, enabling us to conduct research that would not have been possible at our own institution.					
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
The required set of Health & Safety documents were prepared in advance. IREC shared with us all HSE documentation and other policies, making it very smoothly to start the work.					
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
The required set of Health & Safety documents were prepared in advance. IREC shared with us all HSE documentation and other policies.					
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				

As with all chemical research, some of the chemicals have to be disposed appropriately following the current legislation. IREC were very helpful with that to ensure that everything went smoothly in the lab with the experiments conducted.											
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
N/A											
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No										
Some of the chemicals used (e.g. acids, alkalis) can cause harm if H&S measures are not considered. However, as previously discussed before, all the HSE policy at IREC was properly applied and current legislation followed with no problems at all.											
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
N/A											
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
N/A											
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No										
Rigorous application of HSE policies in IREC and appropriate disposal of chemical waste prevent this from happening.											
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
N/A											
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>							
We are genuinely impressed with this research and collaboration with IREC, and foresee future collaboration in projects, research exchanges and preparation of research proposals.											

Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
N/A											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
For high TRL levels, it would be beneficial to have more engagement from the private sector, not just in terms of facilitating industrial access to academic facilities, but the other way around. Showcasing some case studies of companies getting involved in TNAs would also be beneficial.											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No										
I was aware of the pro-active innovation support though all the information available in the website.											
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Due to the nature of the project and the specific research, no engagement was necessary. However, the PhD student involved in the research, may engage more with the pro-active innovation support over the next few months as their PhD comes to an end. In that case, all the resources and training available through StoRIES would be very beneficial if the PhD student is able to access to them.											
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>							
The information provided is very useful, but not very accessible. Having a specific section of the project website dedicated to this (and easy to access) would be very helpful.											

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

